

GES4SEAS POLICY BRIEF #1

THE METHOD OF CHOOSING TOOLS TO SUPPORT ECOSYSTEM-BASED MANAGEMENT AND MARINE ECOSYSTEM MANAGERS – SEAS4GES

How can this Policy Brief support you?

Policy makers and managers need to take transparent, defensible and robust decisions to inform ecosystem-based management (EBM). The SEAS4GES (Selection of Ecosystem-based Approaches 4 Good Environmental Status) is a novel decision support system that guides policy-advisors and scientists in selecting optimal tools to effectively and efficiently undertake marine quality assessments.

Key Messages

There are many, varied types of assessments that can be used to support marine EBM; these can be summarised into 18 elements (see Table 1).

Different tools are available, alone or in combination, to assess an EBM element and other marine challenges but users need to know which tool(s) to choose.

That choice not only depends on the tool capability to respond to the assessment question, but also on the resources available to the user.

The software SEAS4GES is a novel and user-friendly system to help practitioners (who are not necessarily experts) make that choice.

Table 1 EBM elements Requiring Suitable Tools

1 Cumulative effects assessments (CEA)	7 Pressures-Activities footprints	13 Climate change
2 MSFD assessments of Good Environmental Status	8 Effects footprints (and/or Impact footprints)	14 Pressure and impact reduction/mitigation
3 Whole ecosystem assessments	9 Links between activities, pressures and impacts	15 Spatial and other measures
4 Ecosystem Services and societal goods and benefits (delivery, impacts, valuation)	10 Single MSFD Descriptors/single issues (e.g., eutrophication, Non-Indigenous Species, Harmful Algal Blooms)	16 Uncertainty
5 Specific biotic effects/impacts	11 Single species / Ecosystem Components state change	17 Risks
6 Specific ecosystem functions (and impacts on functions)	12 Threatened habitats and species	18 Other policy requirements (e.g., Maritime Spatial Planning Directive, Birds and Habitats Directives, Biodiversity Strategy)

Narrative

The requirements to support marine EBM have been defined and their relevance interrogated in relation to implementing the European Marine Strategy and the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD). The many tools and methods available to address these aspects range from conceptual to empirical and deterministic models, from detailed biogeochemical aspects to end-to-end models, and from natural science to socio-economic approaches.

Identifying the most suitable tool(s) ensures an efficient and effective EBM process. Tool suitability firstly depends on how well the tool functions (i.e., what the tool can do) against that needed to support EBM in the specific case (e.g. the type of assessment to undertake, the type of outputs required, the elements addressed). Secondly, whether the resources (data, skills, expertise) available in the assessment area are sufficient to use the specific tool (e.g. based on its data requirements).

As the available tools have limited uses, the Decision Support System SEAS4GES was developed to aid users in selecting the most appropriate tool(s) for one or more EBM elements. SEAS4GES incorporates the assessment needs and the resources (data and skills) required and available. SEAS4GES is supported by detailed factsheets for each tool, allowing their incorporation into a clearly structured and transparent framework.

Ecosystem Based Management (EBM) as the means to protect the natural system while delivering societal goods and benefits

Policy implications

The Ecosystem-based Approach (EBA) to management is embedded in many marine European Directives and Policies; EBM is the means of operationalising EBA as required by the following legal instruments, amongst others, thereby linking science, policy and management:

European Directives

- Directive 2008/56/EC (MSFD): contribution to Article 1(3)
- Directive 2014/89/EU (MSPD): contribution to Article 5(1)
- Natura 2000 Directives (1992/43/EU and 2009/147/EU)
- Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EU)

Other Policy / International Objectives

- EU Common Fisheries Policy (CFP): contribution to Article 2
- EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030
- Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD): Targets 5, 8 and 11
- European and UNEP Regional Seas Conventions: HELCOM (Baltic Sea), OSPAR (NE Atlantic), Barcelona (Mediterranean), Bucharest (Black Sea) implementation (e.g. COP15 UNEP/DEPI/Decision IG 17/6)
- United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS): contribution to Articles 192 and 194(5)
- UNESCO and UNEP environmental policy guidance
- The Sustainable Development Goals, especially #14, with 13 and 15 and then 3, 7, 8, 9, 12 and 17.

Key Facts

EBM encompasses both natural and human ecosystem components and processes.

EBM includes interactions, cumulative impacts and multiple objectives.

Assessing ecosystem status/condition/health is essential to decide the most appropriate management actions.

Many EBM tools will be needed to determine the success of Programmes of Measures to achieve Good Environmental Status (GES).

Beyond the State of Art

SEAS4GES is an innovative Excel-based decision support system that guides the user through the tool selection process. It identifies suitable tools and also those tools which are unsuitable to support the user. This user-friendly system does not require specialist expertise to be used even if the subsequent use of the selected tool(s) requires specialist knowledge or skills. SEAS4GES therefore aids policy-makers and implementers, policy advisors and researchers in their selection of the most appropriate tool(s) for the relevant EBM element(s).

The SEAS4GES Decision Support System - How it works

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References and resources

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GES4SEAS Deliverable D2.1: <https://zenodo.org/records/13739742>.

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SEAS4GES Tools factsheets: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14760469>.

For additional resources from GES4SEAS project, visit the web page: <https://www.ges4seas.eu>

For more information,
including the SEAS4GES
tool, scan the QR code

Scan view the
guidelines for practical
ecosystem approach

